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THERMODYNAMIC AND ADSORPTION PROPERTIES OF NEEM LEAVES ENHANCED WITH BANANA PEELS AS CORROSION INHIBITORS FOR MILD STEEL IN SEA WATER

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion is the deterioration of materials by chemical interaction with their environment. The consequences of corrosion are many and varied, e.g structural failure or breakdown etc. Though many synthetic compounds like chromates, Lead, nitrides, phosphates and benzoates showed good anticorrosive activity, most of them are highly toxic to both human beings and environment. The extract of Neem leaves was hybridised with Banana peels extract and subjected to corrosion test using weight loss and thermometric method with mild steel flat bar coupon. The corrosion inhibition mechanism of Neem leaves and Banana peels extracts in sea water and 2.0 M H₂SO₄ show that the inhibition efficiency (IE) increases with increase in concentration but decreases with increase in temperature for all the inhibitors throughout the test period, indicating a physisorption of extract on the mild steel surface. The values of activation energy (E_a) were found to range from 30.73KJ/mol-42.95KJ/mol and 26.23KJ/mol-34.89KJ/mol for different percentage of inhibitors in sea water and H₂SO₄ solution respectively. The range of values gotten for the inhibitors used were higher than that of the blank indicating that the corrosion of mild steel is retarded by the presence of the inhibitors in sea water and H₂SO₄ media. In conclusion, hybridization can be used to increase the inhibition efficiency of plant extract.

Keywords: Inhibitor, Temperature, Corrosion, Hybridize, Solution, Physisorption, Adsorption, Thermodynamic

INTRODUCTION

The interaction between the metal surface and its environment, which degrades the metallic properties of metals through chemical or electrochemical attack, by its environment is called corrosion (Anvers, 2000). It poses significant industrial challenges including, reduction of metal thickness leading to loss of mechanical strength and structural failure or breakdown, hazards or injuries to people arising from structural failure or breakdown (e.g. bridges, cars, aircraft), reduced value of goods due to deterioration of appearance etc. The most widely used metal is mild steel. Corrosion inhibitors are substances which when added in small concentrations to corrosive media decrease or prevent the reaction of the metal with the media (Erunoso, 2011). A corrosion inhibitor is a substance that could significantly reduce the corrosion rate of a metal (Dong et al., 2011; Obot et al., 2019).

Though many synthetic compounds like chromates, Lead, nitrides, phosphates and benzoates showed good anticorrosive activity, most of them are highly toxic to both human beings and environment (Al-mamun et al., 2020). The use of chemical inhibitors has been limited because of the environmental threat and environmental regulations. These inhibitors may cause reversible (temporary) or irreversible (permanent) damage to organ system, namely, kidneys or liver, or disturbing a biochemical process. These known hazardous effects of most synthetic corrosion inhibitors are the motivation for the use of some natural products as corrosion inhibitors (Eddy & Ebenso, 2008).

The use of plant extracts as corrosion inhibitors have become important because they are environmentally acceptable, inexpensive, readily available and renewable sources of materials and ecologically acceptable. phytochemical constituents of plant extract, such as saponnin, tannin, alkaloid, glycoside, amino acid, organic acid, pigments, anthraquinone and flavanoid are the factors that determine the inhibition efficiency of the plant extract (Eddy & Ebenso, 2008).

In a country like Nigeria where neem leaves and banana peels are in abundance and are regarded as waste, if they are used as corrosion inhibitor, it will make our environment less prone to pollution. If corrosion is prevented, the money loss to corrosion can be channeled to other uses like creation of employment especially in developing countries like Nigeria where many are jobless and poverty level is high.

Naturally occurring substances have been used successfully as corrosion inhibitor and have been reported by some researchers: Thermodynamic and Optimization Studies of Castor Leaf Extract as Corrosion Inhibitor on Stainless Steel 301 (Okewale & Adebayo, 2020); Exploration of coffee bean husks waste as an eco-environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor on mild steel in sulphuric acid solutions (Gusti et al., 2020); Adsorption and Inhibitive Properties of Ethanol Extracts of *Musa Sapientum* Peels as a Green Corrosion Inhibitor for Mild Steel in H_2SO_4 (Eddy & Ebenso, 2008); Inhibition of Mild Steel Corrosion in Acidic Medium by *Allium Sativum* (Okafor et al., 2005); Industrial Application and Inhibition Properties of *Cucurbita Maxima* on Metal Corrosion in Aggressive Media (Omotiona et al., 2024); evaluation of palm leaf as a viable inhibitor for mitigation of mild steel corrosion in hydrochloric acid medium (Omotiona et al., 2024); Adsorptive and thermodynamic properties of methanol extract of *Toona sinensis* leaves for the corrosion of mild steel in HCl medium (Emriadi et al., 2016); Adsorption and corrosion of renewable inhibitor of Pomelo peel extract for mild steel in phosphoric acid solution (Lin et al., 2021); Corrosion Inhibition of Iron in Hydrochloric Acid Solution by Jojoba Oil (Chetoauni et al., 2004); Inhibitive Action of *Delonix Regia* Extract for the Corrosion of Aluminium in Acidic Medium (Abiola et al., 2007); Inhibition of Acid Corrosion of Mild Steel by *Telfaria Accidentalis* Extract (Oguzie, 2005).

Most green corrosion inhibitors are obtained from ethanol, acid, methanol, or formaldehyde extract of plant materials (Odiongenyi 2009). *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) is a plant grown for ornamental purpose and as a wind breaker. It generally contains significant amount of water soluble electrochemically active compounds, as well as high concentrations of alkaloids, fatty acids, nitrogen- and oxygen-containing compounds. However, the inhibitive effect of aqueous extract of neem leaves is not encouraging despite its abundance. It was found to be 31.6% on the corrosion of mild steel at 30°C in 5M H_2SO_4 solution (Okafor et al., 2005). *Musa Sapientum* which is commonly called Banana is cultivated throughout the tropic primarily for its fruits (Anhwange, 2009). It peels when discarded constitute solid waste which is a problem in Nigeria because of lack of solid waste management (Olafadehan & Salami, 2011). *Musa Sapientum peel* contains numerous chemical constituents which include: saponins, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, resins, terpenes, and phenolic (Erunoso, 2011). The inhibitive effects of aqueous extracts of Banana peels was found to be 98% on the corrosion protection of mild steel in sea water by means of weight loss method (Sangeetha et al., 2012).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the availability of Neem leaves, the efficiency of its corrosion inhibition is low, because saponin which is a key chemical component in corrosion inhibition is not found in neem leaves. Corrosion of metals is a serious environmental problem that has been given adequate attention in the oil and gas industries because during industrial processes such as acid cleaning and etching, metal surfaces often come in contact with acidic medium (e.g. H₂SO₄), which could lead to corrosion. Existing inhibitors like lead compounds, Chromate, nitrides, phosphates and benzoates are no longer acceptable because of their harmful effects on the environment, scarcity and its high cost couple with the fact that the value of naira is falling. Neem leaf and Banana peel constitute environmental nuisance and pollution when burnt, and primarily because Nigeria is not proactive in the management of her solid waste.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this work is to improve the corrosion inhibition characteristics of Neem leaf extract through hybridization with banana peels extract. The specific objectives are to:

- i. hybridize neem leaves extract with Banana peels extract with a view to improving the efficiency of the neem leaf extract.
- ii. test the inhibitive efficiency of the hybridized extracts using mild steel in H₂SO₄, sea water and at varying temperatures.
- iii. determine the adsorption kinetics of the extracts on the metal surface.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research aims to address the following research questions:

- i. Can neem leaves extract be hybridized with banana peel extract in order to improve its inhibition efficiency?
- ii. What is the inhibition efficiency of the hybridized inhibitor using mild steel in sea water, H₂SO₄ and at varying temperature?
- iii. What is the adsorption kinetic of the extract on mild steel in sea water and H₂SO₄?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The interaction between the metal surface and its environment, which degrades the metallic properties of metals through chemical or electrochemical attack, by its environment is called corrosion (Anvers, 2000). It poses significant industrial challenges including, reduction of metal thickness leading to loss of mechanical strength and structural failure or breakdown, hazards or injuries to people arising from structural failure or breakdown (e.g. bridges, cars, aircraft), reduced value of goods due to deterioration of appearance etc. The most common and important electrochemical reactions in the corrosion of iron are thus (Librini et al., 2010).

Anodic reaction (corrosion)

Cathodic reactions (simplified)

Or

Reaction 2a is most common in acids and in the pH range 6.5 – 8.5. The most important reaction is oxygen reduction 2b. In this latter case corrosion is usually accompanied by the formation of solid corrosion debris from the reaction between the anodic and cathodic products.

Pure iron (II) hydroxide is white but the material initially produced by corrosion is normally a greenish colour due to partial oxidation in air.

Further hydration and oxidation reactions can occur and the reddish rust that eventually forms is a complex mixture whose exact constitution will depend on other trace elements which are present. Because the rust is precipitated as a result of secondary reactions it is porous and absorbent and tends to act as a sort of harmful poultice which encourages further corrosion. If solid corrosion products are produced directly on the surface as the first result of anodic oxidation these may provide a highly protective surface film which retards further corrosion, the surface is then said to be “passive”. An example of such a process would be the production of an oxide film on iron in water, a reaction which is encouraged by oxidizing conditions or elevated temperatures (Librini et al., 2010).

Certain factors can tend to accelerate the action of a corrosion cell. These include: i. Establishment of well-defined locations on the surface for the anodic and cathodic reactions and ii. The nature of the environment. Corrosion can be prevented by retarding either the anodic or cathodic reactions. This can be achieved in several ways (Rani et al., 2010). Conditioning the metal, electrochemical control and conditioning the corrosive environment e.g removal of oxygen and corrosion inhibitor.

Corrosion inhibitors are substances which when added in small concentrations to corrosive media decrease or prevent the reaction of the metal with the media (Erunosos, 2011). A corrosion inhibitor is a substance that could significantly reduce the corrosion rate of a metal (Dong et al., 2021; Obot et al., 2019). Inhibitors are classified according to their action (as anodic, cathodic and mixed inhibitors) and according to their mechanism of action (as hydrogen evolution, scavengers, vapour-phase and adsorption inhibitors) (Singh et al., 2012).

Corrosion can be measure by the use of the following methods: Weight loss method, thermometry method, polarization techniques, hydrogen evolution, gasometric method, electrochemical measurement and gravimetric measurements.

Review of Related Research Work

Naturally occurring substances like plants with its products have been tried as corrosion inhibitors for metals and alloys in acidic and other corrosive medium and were found successfull as corrosion inhibitor as reported by some researchers. Salami et al (2008), investigated *Musa Sapientum* peels extract as a corrosion inhibitor on mild steel in 2.0 M H₂SO₄ using weight loss method. The results of the study showed inhibitor efficiency of approximately 71 % for 0.8 g/l extract.

Okafor et al (2010) investigated the inhibitive action of leaves (LV), root (RT) and seeds (SD) extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on mild steel corrosion in H₂SO₄ solutions using weight loss and gasometric techniques. The results obtained show that the seed (SD) have the highest corrosion inhibition efficiency followed by the Root (RT) and the least was the leaves (LV). A mechanism of chemical adsorption of the phytochemical components of the

plant extracts on the surface of the metal is proposed for the inhibition behavior. The experimental data fit into the Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Loto et al (2011) studied the effect of *Carica Papaya* (Pawpaw) leaves and *Camellia Sinensis* (tea) extracts as an organic green inhibitor on the corrosion of α β (duplex) brass (65-35% Cu-Zn alloy) in 1M HNO₃ (nitric acid) at ambient temperature. Weight loss and potential measurement techniques were used for the experimental work. The tea extract was obtained from the green tea leaves. The results obtained showed effective corrosion inhibition of the extracts on the brass test specimens in the 1M Nitric acid used. The combined extracts also gave good corrosion inhibition performance. The test specimen (duplex brass) gave some appreciable corrosion resistance in the test environment. With Pawpaw extracts the best performance was more of 25% concentration addition to the test environment. With the extracts of green tea the best result for corrosion inhibition was obtained with the 100% concentration.

Ayo et al (2013) studied Stress Corrosion Cracking (SCC) results from the combined action of three factors: the tensile stresses in the material, a corrosive medium and elevated temperature. In this study, the stress corrosion cracking and micro-structural analysis of mild steel immersed in orange juice medium was investigated using weight loss technique and SEM analysis. The mild steel coupons were heat treated to various austenitic temperatures, cooled in water and immersed in orange juice. The weight losses of the mild steel samples were measured at a two days interval and the corrosion rate was determined. The results obtained show that SCC relative to mild steel is mainly a function of the acidity of the medium under study, and the corrosion rate increases with increase in exposure time. Also, the higher the austenitic temperature the more the resistance to corrosion attack due to higher hardness obtained at higher temperatures. The SEM analysis revealed that the transgranular and intergranular attacks were visibly responsible for the corrosion of this material in this medium. The evolution of hydrogen at low pH of the medium due to the presence of acidic citric acid eliminated the possibility of protective formation on the mild steel throughout the exposure period.

Similarly, some empirical studies were carried out by some researchers to determine the inhibition efficiency of some plants, such as Ngobiria et al (2013) who investigated Inhibition of pseudo-anaerobic corrosion of oil pipeline steel in pipeline water using biomass-derived molecules. Taleb et al (2011) studied the inhibitive effect of naturally available Potato peel extract (PPE) toward the corrosion of mild steel in 2M HCl solution by weight loss and electrochemical techniques. El bribri (2015) studied the temperature effects on carbon steel corrosion in molar HCl solution, in the absence and presence of methanolic extract of *Euphorbia Falcata.L* (MEEF) using Gravimetric method. Ferry et al (2013) studied extracts of *Allium Cepa* (Onion) used as natural corrosion inhibitors on mild steel in seawater by immersion technique. Ayssar et al (2012) studied the inhibition and the effect of temperature and concentration of trans-4-hydroxy-4'-stilbazole on the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution by weight loss experiments at temperatures ranging from 303 to 343 K. Nurul et al (2013) studied the corrosion inhibition mechanism of the *Curcuma longa* extract on mild steel surface in 1M HCl at different temperatures (30-55°C) by gravimetric measurements. Inhibition efficiency values increase with the inhibitor concentration but decrease with rise in temperature suggesting physisorption.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and apparatus

Fresh samples of banana peels and neem leaves were collected and washed carefully with distill water to remove any form of dirt and dried under the sun. The dried leaves and peels were grounded using grinder to powdered form. The sheets of mild steel used for this study were cut into flat coupons and washed with ethanol to remove any form of grease or oxide before used. The fine powdered of the different samples were completely soaked in ethanol solution for 24 hours after which the mixtures were stirred properly in order to have homogenous solution and then filtered. The filtrates were subjected to evaporation process and concentration using Soxhlet apparatus to remove the ethanol in the filtrate. The different extracts were obtained in its pure form at the end of the evaporation process.

Figure 1 below shows how mixture of extract in ethanol solution were stirred.

Fig 1 stirring of mixture of extract in ethanol solution

The experiment was carried out at Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria. The following apparatus were used to carried out the work: Beakers and conical flask (borosilicate, 250ml and 500ml)-for preparation of solution and settings of experiment; distiller (micro field instrument)-for preparation of distilled water; digital weigh balance (model-Ohaus, 3 digit balance)-for weight measurement; water bath (model-HSS1, 300w)-for experiment at higher temperature (353k, 363k and 373k); stop watch (glass type)-for immersion time period and Soxhlet apparatus (model-KDM-A, volume-500ml, heating power 300w)-for extraction and concentration of banana peels and neem leaves.

Sea water and Preparation of Acid Solutions

The sea water used for this experiment was obtain from Lagos sea. The standard concentrated 2.0 M H₂SO₄ acid used for this research has a density of 1.84g/cm, percentage purity of 98% and molar mass of 98g/mol.

To obtain the molarity of the concentrated H₂SO₄ acid, the following relation was used (Yawas 2005):

$$\text{Molarity} = \frac{\text{concentration}}{\text{molar mass}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Concentration} = \text{standard volume} \times \text{density} \times \text{percentage purity}$$

For 1 litre (1000cm³) of standard H₂SO₄ acid,

$$\text{Concentration} = 1000 \times 1.84 \times 98\%$$

Hence the molarity is given as:

$$\text{Molarity} = \frac{1000 \times 1.84 \times 98}{98} = 18.40\text{M}$$

Similarly, the volume of standard H₂SO₄ acid required for 1000ml of 2.0M H₂SO₄ was obtained from the relation $C_1 \times V_1 = C_2 \times V_2$ (2)

Where C=concentration, and

V=volume

Since 1000ml of 2.0M H₂SO₄ acid is required,

Hence,

$$18.4 \times V_1 = 2 \times 1000$$

$$V_1 = \frac{2 \times 1000}{18.40} = 108.7 \text{ml}$$

Therefore 108.7ml acid was dissolved in 1000ml of distilled water in a standard flask to obtain the desired concentration.

Method

The extract of neem leaves was hybridised with banana peels extract and subjected to corrosion test using weight loss method with mild steel flat bar coupon at temperatures ranging from 353 to 373 K in sea water and 2M H₂SO₄ solution. The method involves exposing a clean weighed piece of mild steel to the corrosive solution and weighing the piece to determine the loss of weight. Here, mild steel specimen was immersed separately in sea water and 2.0 M H₂SO₄ solution at temperatures ranging from 353 to 373 K. Every sample was weighed by a digital weigh balance and then placed in the acidic solution.

Weight Loss Method

Corrosion Rate

The corrosion rate (CR) in millimeters penetration per year (mm/y) was calculated from equation 3.1 (Callister, 1996).

$$C.R = \frac{87.6W}{DAT} \quad (3)$$

Where, W is weight loss (mg), A is the total area of sample in cm², T is time of exposure in hours and D is the density of mild steel = 7.87g/cm³.

Weight Loss Ratio

$$\text{Weight Loss Ratio is expressed as: Weight loss ratio (W. R)} = \frac{\text{weight loss of specimen in inhibited solution}}{\text{weight loss of specimen in uninhibited solution}} \quad (4)$$

Inhibitor efficiency

The inhibitor efficiency (IE) is compute using the relationship in equation 9 (Loto et al 2011).

$$IE = \frac{(C.R)_o - (C.R)}{(C.R)_o} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

Where (C.R)_o and (C.R) are the corrosion rate in (mm/y) without and with different concentrations and percentages of inhibitor.

Surface coverage

The degree of surface coverage (θ) for different concentration of the inhibitor in acidic media was computed using equation 3.4 (Khaled, 2008).

$$\theta = \frac{(C.R.)_o - (C.R.)}{(C.R.)_o} \tag{6}$$

Thermodynamic and adsorption considerations

Values of activation energy for the corrosion reaction of mild steel in the presence and absence of inhibitors was calculated using the Arrhenius equation (eqn 11).

$$CR = A_i \exp(-E_a / RT) \tag{7}$$

Taking logarithm of both sides of equation 11, equation 12 was obtained:

$$\text{Log CR} = \text{Log } A_i - \frac{E_a}{2.303RT} \tag{8}$$

Where CR is the corrosion rate of mild steel, A_i is Arrhenius constant or pre-exponential factor, E_a is the activation energy of the reaction, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature. Considering a change in temperature from 353 K (T_1) to 373K (T_2), the corresponding values of the corrosion rates at these temperatures are ρ_1 and ρ_2 respectively. Inserting these parameters into equation 12, equation 13 is obtained:

$$\log \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1} = \frac{E_a}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \tag{9}$$

Values of E_a for the inhibited corrosion reaction of mild steel was calculated using equation 9. For a physical adsorption, it is expected that the value of E_a should be less than 80.00KJ/mol (Ebenso, 2003; Ebenso, 2004; & Sheatty, 2006). The values of heat of adsorption of inhibitors on mild steel surface was calculated using equation 10 (Ebenso 2003; Ebenso 2004; Sheatty 2006).

$$Q_{ads} = 2.303R \left[\log \left(\frac{\theta_2}{1-\theta_2} \right) - \log \left(\frac{\theta_1}{1-\theta_1} \right) \right] \times \left(\frac{T_1 \times T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \right) \text{ KJ/m} \tag{10}$$

Where θ_1 and θ_2 were the degrees of surface coverage at the temperatures, T_1 (323 K) and T_2 (363 K), respectively.

Adsorption isotherms are very important in understanding the mechanism of inhibition of corrosion reactions. The most frequently used adsorption isotherms are Frumkin, Temkin, Freundlich, Florry Huggins, Bockris – Swinkel, El-Awardy and Langmuir isotherms. All these isotherms can be represented as follows,

$$f(\theta, x) \exp(-2a\theta) = Kc \tag{11}$$

Where $f(\theta, x)$ is the configuration factor which depends upon the physical model and the assumptions underlying the derivation of the isotherm. θ is the degree of surface coverage, C is the inhibitor concentration in the electrolyte, x is the size ratio, a, is molecular interaction parameter and k is the equilibrium constant of the adsorption process Langmuir isotherm is an ideal isotherm for physical or chemical adsorption where there is no interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent. Assumptions of Langmuir relate the concentration of the adsorbate in the bulk of the electrolyte (C) to the degree of surface coverage (θ) according to equation 10 (Umoren & Ebenso, 2008):

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K} + C \tag{12}$$

Where k is the equilibrium constant of adsorption, C is the inhibitor concentration (mol/l). Taking logarithm of both sides of equation 16, equation 17 is obtained:

$$\log (C/\theta) = \log C - \log K \tag{13}$$

The free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) according to equation 18 (Zhang and Hua 2009).

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -2.303RT\log(55.5K) \tag{14}$$

Or $\Delta G_{ads} = RT\ln(55.5K)$

where R is the gas constant or universal gas constant (0.00831447 KJ), T is the absolute temperature in kelvin, K is the equilibrium constant of adsorption, ΔG_{ads} Gibbs energy of adsorption (KJ/mole) and 55.5 is the molar concentration of H_2SO_4 or the concentration of water in solution in mol/l.

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RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Corrosion Rate

Table 1 show the weight loss, corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency of neem leaves, banana peel extracts and hybrid inhibitor in sea water.

Table 1: Weight loss, Corrosion rate and Inhibitor efficiency (IE) of neem leaves, banana peel extracts and hybrid inhibitor in sea water.

In sea water solution	Exposure Time(hr)	Initial Weight(g)	Final Weight(g)	Weight Loss(g)	Corrosion Rate CR (mm/y)	IE%	θ
Sea water	312	7.500	7.358	0.142	0.19377		
100% Neem	312	7.550	7.480	0.070	0.0958	58.83	0.5883
100% Banana	312	7.727	7.710	0.017	0.02308	93.31	0.9331
hybrid	312	7.935	7.904	0.027	0.03700	85.00	0.8500

The results of corrosion inhibition of plant extracts in sea water were obtained. The results of the experiment have shown that in sea water, Banana peels extract had maximum inhibition efficiency of 93.31% while Neem leaves extract had 58.83%. It means Banana peels extract inhibit corrosion far better than Neem leaves extract, this agree with Sangeetha et al (2012) and Okafor et al (2010). The results also showed that the hybridized inhibitors (Banana and Neem), inhibited corrosion. The hybridized inhibitors had the optimum inhibitor efficiency of 85% in sea water. Clearly, at this combination, the inhibition efficiency is much more than that of Neem. In essence, hybridized sample has shown improvement in inhibition efficiency of Neem.

Table 2 below show the weight loss, corrosion rate and Inhibitor efficiency (IE) of neem leaves, banana peel extracts and hybrid inhibitor in 2.0 M H_2SO_4

Table 2: Weight loss, Corrosion rate and Inhibitor efficiency (IE) of neem leaves, banana peel extracts and hybrid inhibitor in 2.0 M H₂SO₄

In 2.0 M H ₂ SO ₄ solution	Exposure Time(hr)	Initial Weight(g)	Final Weight(g)	Weight Loss(g)	Corrosion Rate CR (mm/y)	IE%	θ
2.0 M H ₂ SO ₄	216	5.992	1.417	4.575	9.41429		
100% Neem	216	7.180	5.233	1.947	3.75991	57.46	0.5746
100% Banana	216	5.089	4.450	0.639	1.28658	88.53	0.8853
hybrid	216	5.631	4.754	0.877	1.73209	83.27	0.8327

In H₂SO₄, the result showed that Banana peels and Neem leaves extract inhibit corrosion, but Banana had 88.53% inhibitor efficiency which is higher than 57.46% of Neem. The hybridized inhibitors inhibited corrosion to some extent in H₂SO₄. The hybridized extract had the optimum inhibitor efficiency of 83.27%. The inhibition efficiency of Banana and Neem is higher in sea water than H₂SO₄, indicating that H₂SO₄ media is more corrosive than sea water. The inhibitor efficiency of the hybridized inhibitor is encouraging and this can be used in the industries as a substitute for the imported chemical inhibitors which will save the country a huge amount of money use for importation of inhibitors. In addition, using the Banana peels extract to hybridize Neem leaves extract is a way of managing waste because the peels and leaves constitute solid waste which its management is a problem in Nigeria, as observed by Olafadehan and Salami (2011). The facts that the Banana extract is a natural extract which is environment friendly and nontoxic to human can also be consider.

Effect of temperature

Table 3 below show the corrosion rate of mild steel in sea water in the absence of inhibitors at different temperature (353-373K).

Table 3: Corrosion rate of mild steel in sea water in the absence of inhibitors at different temperature (353-373K).

Temperature (k)	Exposure Time (hr)	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	Weight Loss (g)	Corrosion Rate CR (mm/y)	LOG CR	LOG CR/T
353	1	7.516	7.505	0.013	5.54412	0.743833	-1.80394
	2		7.491	0.027	5.75735	0.760223	-1.78755
	3		7.478	0.038	5.54411	0.743832	-1.80394
	4		7.462	0.054	5.75735	0.760223	-1.78755
363	1	7.520	7.505	0.015	6.39706	0.805980	-1.75393
	2		7.489	0.031	6.61029	0.820221	-1.73969
	3		7.472	0.045	6.39706	0.805980	-1.75393
	4		7.453	0.062	6.61029	0.820221	-1.73969
373	1	7.582	7.564	0.018	7.67647	0.885162	-1.68655
	2		7.543	0.035	7.46323	0.872927	-1.69878
	3		7.524	0.054	7.67647	0.885162	-1.68655
	4		7.502	0.074	7.88970	0.897060	-1.67465

Table 4 below show the weight loss, corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in sea water, with hybridized inhibitor at different temperature (353-373K)

Table 4: weight loss, corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in sea water, with hybridized inhibitor at different temperature (353-373K)

Temp. (k)	Exposure Time (hr)	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	Weight Loss (g)	Corrosion Rate (mm/y)	IE%	θ	LOG CR	LOG (CR/T)
353	1	7.951	7.946	0.003	1.27843	77.9407	0.77940	0.106677	-2.44110
	2		7.940	0.007	1.49150	76.0939	0.76094	0.173624	-2.37415
	3		7.934	0.011	1.56253	73.8165	0.73816	0.193828	-2.35395
	4		7.928	0.018	1.91765	78.6922	0.78692	0.282769	-2.26501
363	1	7.937	7.931	0.004	1.70458	73.3537	0.73354	0.231616	-2.32829
	2		7.926	0.009	1.91765	73.9900	0.73990	0.282769	-2.27714
	3		7.920	0.014	2.12125	74.8402	0.74840	0.326592	-2.23331
	4		7.914	0.022	2.34379	72.5433	0.72543	0.369919	-2.18999
373	1	7.962	7.955	0.005	2.13072	70.2435	0.70243	0.328526	-2.24318
	2		7.952	0.014	2.55686	72.7405	0.68741	0.407707	-2.16400
	3		7.946	0.019	2.54191	71.8870	0.69887	0.405160	-2.16655
	4		7.938	0.025	2.66340	70.2421	0.66242	0.425436	-2.14627

From the result obtained it was found that the inhibition efficiency in sea water decreases with increase in temperature. The same trend was followed in H₂SO₄ solution. The significant difference between values of inhibition efficiency obtained at 353, 363 and 373 K suggests that the mechanism of adsorption of inhibitor on mild steel surface is by physical adsorption. For a physical adsorption mechanism, inhibition efficiency of an inhibitor decreases with temperature. While for a chemical adsorption mechanism, values of inhibition efficiency increase with temperature as observe by Ebenso (2003) and Abd El-hameed (2011).

The weight loss of low carbon steel and the corrosion rate were found to increase with increases in temperature. This also suggests that the rate of corrosion in both sea water and 2M H₂SO₄ solutions increases with temperature, a trend that supports the mechanism of physical adsorption. This could lead to the conclusion that the protective films of the inhibitors formed on the surface of the specimen of the low carbon steel are less stable at higher temperature. Which may be due to the desorption of some adsorbed molecules from the surface of the mild steel at higher temperature leading to the greater area of steel been exposed to the acidic environment.

Kinetic Parameter of Activation (*Adsorption Kinetics of the Extracts on the Metal Surface*)

Table 5 show the corrosion Kinetic (Activation) parameters for the corrosion of mild steel in sea water in the absence and presence of different percentage of inhibitors

Table 5: Corrosion Kinetic (Activation) parameters for the corrosion of mild steel in sea water in the absence and presence of different percentage of inhibitors

% of inhibitors in sea water in ratio of neem and banana extract	E _a (KJ/mol)	ΔH _a (KJ/mol)	E _a - ΔH _a (KJ/mol)
Blank	22.40	20.26	2.14
90:10	30.73	28.27	2.46
80:20	40.70	37.91	2.79
70:30	32.77	30.25	2.52
60:40	32.05	29.42	2.63
50:50	42.95	40.20	2.75

The calculated values of E_a-ΔH_a are close to RT (2.67KJ/mol). This result shows the inhibitor acted equally on E_a and ΔH_a.

The activation energy (E_a) were calculated and they values were found to range from 30.73KJ/mol-42.95KJ/mol and 26.23KJ/mol-34.89KJ/mol for different percentage of inhibitors in sea water and H_2SO_4 solution respectively. The range of values gotten for the different percentage of inhibitors used were higher than that of the blank indicating that the corrosion of mild steel is retarded by the presence of the different percentage of inhibitors in sea water and H_2SO_4 media. It can also be observed that the activation energy is lower than the threshold value of 80KJ/mol. The results achieved in this study is comparable to that described by Okewale and Adebayo (2020) and Gusti et al (2020) required for the mechanism of chemical adsorption. Therefore, the adsorption of the inhibitors on the mild steel surface supports the mechanism of physical adsorption (physisorption). Higher values of E_a in the presence of inhibitor are a good indication that the extract increases the energy barrier for the corrosion process.

Table 6 show the corrosion Kinetic (Activation) parameters for the corrosion of mild steel in 2 M H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of different percentage of inhibitors

% of inhibitors in sea water in ratio of neem to banana	E_a (KJ/mol)	ΔH_a (KJ/mol)	$E_a-\Delta H_a$ (KJ/mol)
Blank	18.90	16.39	2.51
90:10	28.15	26.41	1.74
80:20	26.75	24.32	2.43
70:30	26.23	23.72	2.51
60:40	26.41	24.32	2.09
50:50	34.89	32.57	2.32

Table 6: Corrosion Kinetic (Activation) parameters for the corrosion of mild steel in 2 M H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of different percentage of inhibitors

The large positive value of ΔH_a indicates that the corrosion of mild steel was inhibited by the extracts. The high activation energy in the inhibitors presence further supports the proposal of physisorption mechanism. The calculated values of $E_a-\Delta H_a$ are close to RT (2.67KJ/mol). This result shows that the inhibitor acted equally on E_a and ΔH_a , it agrees with Zarrouk et al (2011) and Abd El-hameed (2011). The plots of $\log CR/T$ against reciprocal of absolute temperature from alternative formulation of Arrhenius equation (transition state equation) which gave a straight line in form of a linear graph with slope equal to $-\Delta H_a/2.303R$ and the intercept equal to $\log A$. The enthalpy of activation ($-\Delta H_a$) were calculated and tabulated for the different percentage of inhibitors in the two (2) different media (sea water and H_2SO_4).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion neem leaves extract with optimum IE of 58.83% and 57.46% was improved to 82.19% and 79.05% IE by Banana peels extract when mixed with Banana peels extracts in both sea water and H_2SO_4 solution. The corrosion inhibition mechanism of Neem leaves, Banana peels extracts and hybridized inhibitors in 2.0 M H_2SO_4 and sea water show that the inhibition efficiency (IE) decreases with increase in temperature for all the inhibitors throughout the test period, indicating a physisorption of extract on the mild steel surface. Increase in temperature increases the rate of corrosion and with less stability of the films found on the metal surface resulting to less protection of the metal. Values of activation energy (E_a) of the inhibited corrosion reaction of mild steel are greater than the value obtained for the blank, indicating that the corrosion of mild steel is retarded by the presence of the different percentage of inhibitors in sea water and H_2SO_4 media. The hybridized extract can be used as corrosion inhibitor and make the environment free of toxic chemical inhibitor and less prone to pollution. Adsorption characteristics of the inhibitor follow physical adsorption mechanism. From the study, it was concluded that the hybridized inhibitor is good adsorption inhibitor for the corrosion of mild steel.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The inhibiting action of the extracts (hybridized) on non-ferrous alloys at various temperatures could be investigated.
2. Mediums such as crude oil, Hcl, distillate fuels etc. could be use to characterize the inhibition propensity of these inhibitors.
3. The present research work was carried out by weight loss method only. However, subsequent investigation can be carried out using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Tofel Polarization, resistance and gasometric methods.

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